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PROFESSIONAL DEVELOPMENT PROGRAMMES AVAILABLE IN INFORMATION AND COMMUNICATION TECHNOLOGY TO BOOST DIGITAL SKILLS OF TEACHERS IN SELECTED RURAL SCHOOLS IN SOUTH AFRICA

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Abstract

In South Africa, policies indicate that teachers should continue to integrate Information Communication and Technology (ICT) in their teaching in classrooms. The present study aimed to explore professional development programmes available in ICT to boost digital skills of rural teachers in selected rural schools in South Africa. In this study, an exploratory case study research design was adopted. In this research, the study sample was ten participants, which comprised of two deputy principals, two principals, two deputy principals, two head of grades, two senior phase head of department and finally two foundation phase heads of department. The schools that were selected for the study were sampled using purposive sampling method. In this research, data was collected using semi-structure interviews. In this study, the interview data was analyzed using thematic approach. The findings of the study revealed that ICTs are yet to have a significant impact on education practices on what and how people, teachers and pupils in rural schools learn and use ICT in their schools. School managers declared that professional development in ICT is an important skill especially for teachers because as administrators, they may use computer packages to lessen their administrative work and enhance their teaching. the study recommends that School Management Teams in South Africa should familiarize themselves with the technology adoption policies and the training programs available.

Keywords: Professional development, programmes, Information and Communication Technology, digital skills, teachers, rural schools, South Africa

1. Introduction

It is recognized that schools continue using modern delivery modes in classrooms necessitated by the challenges that are experienced, and the emerging trends in the education sector worldwide. In response to this, teachers should undergo continuous professional development in the adoption of technology in classrooms, so that they gain relevant knowledge, skills, and relevant competencies. It is recognized that in South Africa, when most teachers trained, they did not obtain knowledge on the adoption of technology in classrooms (Canese, Paez Amarilla & Rodriguez (2022). In related research, Vemic's (2007) argues that complex problems that exist in schools and educational institutions could only be addressed by embracing technology-based learning within classrooms. In this case, it improves teachers' skills and knowledge and increases academic performance among learners in classrooms. In a related study, Boyle, et al., (2005) reiterate that using technology-based learning by teachers leads to their empowerment in best practices in classrooms, increased knowledge on technology adoption and better classroom practices for students.

In another research, Gartia (2012) reported that the provision of capabilities and competences to be able to be innovative and address current challenges, makes teachers to be able to improve in their teaching capabilities in classroom. Similarly, Gamage (2006) reiterates that teachers should be trained in modern based teaching to students in classrooms to enhance their skills, understanding and knowledge. However, Chisango, Marongwa, Mtisi & Matyedi, (2019) declare that many teachers felt insecure, with many participants disagreeing that they could fix technical issues if they arose. Thus, continuous teacher training and skills acquisition is regarded as an important part of human capital development (Draker, 2010). In addition, Gamage (2006) reiterates that

undertaking professional development for teachers is beneficial as it brings individual empowerment and overall benefits to the schools. In related research, Wei et al., (2009) reiterates that professional development assists to improve learners' academic performance, enhances teachers' knowledge, content delivery techniques and assessment skills. Mestry (2009) also reported that continuous teacher training on modern technology-based learning improves classroom outcomes, and it makes classrooms to be vibrant and captivating all the time.

The South African rural schools remain disadvantaged on many issues (Luo, Zuo & Wang, 2022) including school infrastructure such as equipment, toilets, telecommunications, buildings and other modern based learning equipment. On the same vein, Naidoo and Perumal (2014) reiterate that schools continue to face myriad problems including large and overcrowded classrooms, lack of ICT knowledge among teachers, inadequate teaching aids in classrooms, and outdated curriculum. Tire and Mlitwa (2008) argue that most teachers in rural areas lack ICT skills and knowledge, and the schools do not have adequate facilities for ICT integration. In addition, schools in rural areas also have other problems such as poor internet connectivity and other technical challenges that limit the ICT integration to facilitate teaching and learning in classrooms. Moreover, Gamage (2006) and Rocha-Castillo, Pasquel-Lopez & Heredia-Escorza, (2025) reiterates that teachers should embrace professional development which would assist in boosting their understanding, knowledge and skills including adoption of technology in classrooms. Thus, the adoption of technology by teachers is likely to benefit them individually and educational institutions. This is also expected to further enhance academic performance among learners. Wei et al., (2009) reiterate that teachers' knowledge, assessment techniques and improved learner academic performance would be realized by teachers who have taken initiatives to pursue professional development courses. In related research, Mestry and Ndhlovu, (2014) argues that the quality of learners' academic performance is only possible with enhanced professional development Initiatives.

In South Africa, policies indicate that teachers should continue using modern based teaching methods in classrooms to ensure that administration efficiency is enhanced in schools (Mestry & Ndhlovu, 2014). In another research, Hussein (2014) argues that teachers should be trained in ICT integration because this is one of the key practices for staff development in schools, thus school management and leadership continue to invest lots of funds and resources on the same. Similarly, Gartia (2012) in agreement with (Rana, 2023) reiterates that teachers are expected to remain relevant to the ever-changing dynamics in classrooms including gaining knowledge, skills and competence. For example, it has been reported that there is a lack of finance to purchase the infrastructure, lack of knowledge on computers for both soft and hardware, and socio-economic disparities which have created a digital divide. Thus, this problem with multifaceted complex necessities is the need for championing related aspects (Morele, 2011). Therefore, many teachers in South Africa lack computer skills, some have negative attitudes towards use of ICT, while others lack access to computer hardware. Moreover, in rural areas, the teachers lack time to attend ICT courses because of the large classes and heavy workload that they are faced with in most parts of the year. This implies that the teachers in schools in rural areas would be better equipped with ICT skills in places that are closer to them due to the prevailing circumstances. Based on the above background, teachers in rural areas need professional development in ICT related aspects in their schools to boost their effectiveness in classroom teaching and learning.

Literature Review

Literature indicates that there are varied professional development initiatives to boost technology competence among teachers that are available in several countries. For example, Uzorka, Namara and Olaniyan (2023) research in Uganda argues that most instructors had low self-efficacy in the use of technology-based learning in classrooms. In addition, Barnová et al., (2020) argues that there should be a major focus on digital technologies for teachers in the professional development emphasizing on the benefits and how to manage emerging challenges that affect classroom practices. Thus, the study reiterates that teachers must be trained on use of technology in classrooms for teaching and learning to be able to be able to handle different and emerging demanding issues that arise among learners. This study underscores the importance of providing in-service teachers with adequate on-going professional development opportunities so that they are equipped with skills to be able to manage current trends and challenges that emerge in classrooms. In emphasizing the adoption of technology to enhance efficacy of teaching in classrooms, Magee et al., (2017) study in USA argues that there is need for teachers to provide and adopt technology as they collaborate with other agencies because the acquired knowledge would make them have increased competence and confidence in managing ever changing dynamic classrooms.

In a systematic study that reiterates the professional development for teachers on adoption of modern based learning, Hennessy et al., (2022) argues that technology use in classrooms continues to evolve and there is need to manage current challenges that emerge in classrooms. The study emphasizes the benefits of technology for teachers and argues that there is need for more and increased attention on availability and accessibility of

technology. On the same vein, Bowman et al., (2022), reiterate on the importance of availability and accessibility of training opportunities can only be enhanced by appropriate teaching and learning skills which are technology based. In a study in Nigeria, leadership roles are key in the provision of professional development in technology adoption and use in classrooms, thus, Uzorka and Olaniyan (2022) affirm that instructors should adopt skills that would assist them in handling emerging issues and challenges in classrooms. This study further reiterates that professional development opportunities for instructors is determined by factors such as policy, support, workload, technology infrastructure available, leadership, and time available among others. To support the above arguments on opportunities and challenges, Maatuk et al., (2022) argue on the information, communication and current teaching styles depend on training, financial support, opportunities for professional development, technology availability, enhanced working conditions, and appropriate technological skills.

In another research that acknowledges the effects of adopting modern teaching methods, Cattaneo, Antonietti and Rauseo (2025) and Muyambi & Ramola (2025) argue for adoption of technology in classrooms, resources for training, opportunities for training and transformative leadership roles are key drivers in implementation of programs that suits instructors and teachers. Furthermore, in response to the research above, Roll and Ifenthaler (2021) argues that there is need for implementation of a model with multiple dimensions to enhance digital competence of teachers and instructors. Thus, the study further reiterates on technology adoption among instructors which includes collaborative networks, positive attitude towards technology use, digital problem competence, digital problem solving and finally a self-reflection on digital communication and environment. Similarly, on emphasizing on quality of digital technology integration in classrooms, Bowman, Vongkulluksn, Jiang and Xie (2020) argue that to enhance technology adoption related skills, the professional development programs should take into consideration factors such as modern classrooms, available resources, teachers' competence, principals leadership styles and roles. The study further revealed that teachers' values should be improved, and their technology skills enhanced when implementing professional development programs to enhance technology skills. Thus, it can be concluded that for classroom tasks, the intensity of adoption of technology for teaching and learning is one of the aspects to be considered when developing and implementing professional development programs for teachers.

Teachers' ability towards integrating technology with the subject content during teaching and learning, has been reported to significantly depend upon teacher training and use of modern teaching strategies in classrooms. For example, a study by Liu et al., (2015) reiterate on comprehensive training empowerment programs for instructors on technology adoption in classrooms includes teaching demonstrations by trainers on technology integration in classrooms. The study further argues that teachers' knowledge and self-efficacy in adopting modern teaching strategies in classrooms depends on the content that is contained in the empowerment and current teaching skills which have been developed. In related study in Uganda, Lubis and Yus (2024) argue that instructors should periodically undergo professional development training opportunities which meet criteria such as specific needs on current technology curriculum, meet their training needs and taught by well-trained trainers in modern teaching techniques in classrooms. In addition, findings further reiterate that appropriate professional development training on technology for teachers should take into consideration factors such as needs of teachers in use of technology, level of training, training facilities available in schools, and finally principles that are adopted in adult education. In a related research that reported positive effects of empowering teachers using current teaching techniques adopted in classrooms, Çam and Koç (2024) argue that after training teachers transferred the knowledge gained to the classrooms, there was increased attention on students from the new teaching methods which included technology adoption, and that there was increased interest demonstrated by students during lessons. Thus, teachers have experienced changed classrooms from the new technology-based teaching methods which brought new insights to students when difficult and challenging topics were being taught in classrooms.

In another related research that examined how professional development of teachers was impacted by adoption of technology-based learning styles, Stutchbury, Ebubedike, Amos and Chamberlain (2023), argued that teachers reported increased positive impact on their classroom practices, professional identity, and enhanced transformational practices that from new teaching methods in classrooms. The study findings also reported that professional development of teachers aims to provide pedagogical change among teachers so that they can make great impact on teaching delivery and student outcomes in classrooms. In addition, it is argued that professional development opportunities led to increased motivation to address pedagogical challenges in classrooms, and there was enhanced positive change in classroom practices leading to improved students' academic performance. Similarly, studies also indicate that professional development and training opportunities for teachers, as argued by Hubers, D. Endedijk and Van Veen (2020) should be characterized by collaboration, coherent content, varied activities, appropriate duration, and focused on technology-based learning in classrooms. In another research that examined the key components of professional development for teachers, Fernández-Batanero, Montenegro-

Rueda, Fernández-Cerero and García-Martínez (2020) reported that technology training is the key training component to enhance quality education. Thus, for effective teacher empowerment and training to be realized, then digital competence of teachers should be taken into consideration, because this will affect its efficacy. This however is in contrast to Mathebula, Moila, Maile & Mnisi (2025) who declare that many countries including South Africa face challenges in integrating ICT in South African region of Gauteng. Finally, research that examined teachers professional development needs, Bergmark (2020) reported that this should contain what teachers think, how to change their ways of thinking, adoption of appropriate classroom based technology, the importance of technology for teaching and learning, bottom-up approach to training, collaboration, integration of technology in classroom contexts and adoption of content specific technology to boost learning in classrooms. Finally, the study suggests a multi-sectoral approach in the empowerment and training of teachers. From reviewed literature above, it is evident that most literature did not capture the rural school contexts, and the present research sought to fill in the research gaps.

Aim of the Study

The present study aimed to explore professional development programmes available in ICT to boost digital skills of rural teachers in selected rural schools in South Africa.

Research Question of the Study

The main research question of the study was stated as follows:

Which professional development programmes available in ICT to boost digital skills of rural teachers exist in selected rural schools in South Africa?

2. Method

Research Design

In this study, an exploratory case study research design was adopted. According to Yin (2012) this design is useful in generating in-depth data and thick descriptions related to the study sample, on their opinions, feelings and knowledge of the subject that is being researched. This research design emphasizes the fact that knowledge is socially constructed by the participants in a particular study. Nieuwenhuis (2012) argues that this research design assists in helping to gain insights into a particular situation. Thus, this design was useful in assisting in generating detailed qualitative data from the research participants.

Study Participants

In this research, the study sample was ten participants, which comprised of two deputy principals, two principals, two deputy principals, two head of grades, two senior phase head of department and finally two foundation phase heads of department. The schools that were selected for the study were sampled using purposive sampling method, with the assumption that they had the data required on teacher professional development in ICT usage in classroom teaching and learning. The study participants were obtained using systematic sampling method because the selection of sample sizes was at every ten. The study participants were relevant for the present study because they are believed to possess adequate information about teacher professional development in schools.

Data Collection Methods

In this research, data was collected using semi-structure interviews. The interviews were relevant in the data collection because they elicited in-depth responses and thick descriptions from the study participants on issues on teacher development problems and challenges in rural areas in schools (Cohen, Manion & Morrison, 2007). Therefore, semi-structured interviews were utilized to obtain detailed data from the research participants. In a related context, Nieuwenhuis (2012) argues that semi-structured interviews should be done in a relaxed manner so that participants feel relaxed, thus each participant was interviewed twice in two months. The researcher utilized an interview protocol to ensure that adequate data was collected. The interview data was audio taped in readiness and preparation for data analysis.

Data Analysis

In this study, the interview data was analyzed using thematic approach. In this approach, the conversations, curricular material and message content from the semi-structured interviews were coded to generate initial data. Thereafter, the coded data were then later grouped into bigger clusters forming themes within the respective research questions that formed the interview schedule (Nieuwenhuis, 2012). In agreement with Merriam (2010)

perspective and proposition, the data that was collected in this research was analyzed to reveal dominance, biases, inequality, sources of power that are within the teachers in rural areas experiences. In addition, the data was analyzed to bring forth how the sources of power were initiated, viewed, transformed, reproduced and maintained social contexts considering social interactions with school principals in each school.

3. Findings

The findings of this study highlighted the importance of teacher professional development (TPD) in ICT as an element of motivation and development to the school as an organization. It emerged from the interview proceedings that the problems behind the accumulation of skills and knowledge of rural educators in ICT is attributable to their principals and managers, some of whom recognize TPD as merely the accumulation of work-related knowledge aspects and lacked understanding of what professional development in ICT is. Some participants, however, referred to ICT as acquiring the necessary skills to use computers for administrative work and as mediating tools to teach.

School managers' understanding of the concept TPD educators in ICT

Participants believed that TPD in ICT use is imperative for school development, the improvement in learner performance and development of computer skills for teachers. School managers declared that professional development in ICT is an important skill especially for teachers because as administrators, they may use computer packages to lessen their administrative work and enhance their teaching. This will eventually contribute to the development of the school as a whole. This included, among others, the improvement of the quality of learners' work, learner performance and assessments as one participant stated:

➤ *"I think it's very necessary because we need to be computer literate and that would make our work very easy in terms of capturing the recordings, the learners names and surnames and just to maybe see the feedbacks and the learners work and the continuous assessment of work that we are doing, so it will be very easy"* (Participant 5)

Participants also stated that when they are computer literate, they can use the computer as a mediating tool between the teacher and the learner. These views support Vygotsky's theory of technology being used as a mediating tool to scaffold information from the teacher to the learner. School managers used words such as knowledge and information to describe their understandings as stated below:

➤ *"..It's knowledge that the teachers must have, the ICT, the computers, how to use computers, and then, maybe how to, how to do some work with the learners using the computers and maybe exposing the laptops and computers, to the learners, and the tablets, to the learners"* (Participant 7)

Participants understanding of the concept of professional development in ICT were primarily referred to the development of computer skills only. This understanding is in contrast to Lloyd's (2005) definition as accessing, acquiring and communicating of information through technological devices. Participants revealed that knowledge of the content and power of computers use in teaching has not increased among them as digital immigrants. This view is also supported by Tire & Mlitwa (2008) who argues that many rural educators do not have ICT support facilities. Participants confirmed this by stating the following:

➤ *"I think, it's it is important if we can learn as educators how to use ICT at school as I don't have full information on this and I need it"* (Participant 1)

➤ *".....most of us don't have the computer skill and nothing is been done, so that educators can be developed in that area. We must develop because it is important to use computers in my teaching".* (Participant 3)

Participants opinions on the professional development of teachers in ICT was in keeping with the *Guidelines for Teacher Training and Professional Development in ICT (Department of Education, 2007)* which highlighted the importance and need for teacher professional development in ICT as equipping educators and with ICT knowledge, skills, values and attitude as these selected participants indicated below:

➤ *"And I also think that maybe teachers could be developed such that everything that they do they should do it, they should use the digital tools, I can say the usage of the digital devices at school level, and maybe it should be something which is not abstract but practical. It's a digital skill we must have"* (Participant 6)

➤ *"Educators should be properly trained on the use of educational technologies. It is important because most of us here, we are the BBC (born before computers) educators, this technology comes now at least I must be trained so that we close that gap, I think now that we must be at the par. They must train us at least so that we must be aware of what is happening in and around".* (Participant 8)

➤ *"I think that um.... the training of school management is not enough.... Educators need to be computer literate".* (Participant 9)

➤ *“They should know how to use computers so that they will impart that knowledge to the learners”.*
(Participant 10)

Participants responses indicated that their perceptions of professional development on the use of ICT are limited because they make mention of computer use only. Participants focused on the development of computer skills and professional development in general. Participants also noted that while the term ICT is commonly used in schools, not all school managers understood the full scope of what exactly it covers. Responding to the question of what the term ICT implied, participants unpacked the concept (ICT) as not encompassing a broad range of technologies but commonly associated it with computers. Participants did not include other informational media, such as handheld devices, television, radio, videos and even printed as part of their definition because they are not exposed to these devices.

Observation notes made during classroom visits clarified the participant’s response to teaching pedagogy. There were no technological devices installed in any of the classrooms. It was observed that teachers taught with no other mediating tools beside the chalk board. Learners were given notes on the board and were asked to write these notes in their exercise books. This was a time consuming and tedious practice for learners because they always wanted clarity on certain unclear words written on the board. Learners do not receive any typed notes. All notes were written on the board. It was also observed that teachers do not use any other form of media such as TVs, videos or tablets to teach. No teaching took place in the computer laboratory because the computers were not working, and the room was used as a place of storage. During another observation session held with school managers, the researcher found that the end of term schedule was hand written. If school managers were computer literate, it could have been done on the computer. School managers were also authorizing and signing lesson plans that were hand written. These observations were clarified by the data gathered during my interview on pedagogy and teacher administration. The marginal impact of ICT on rural pupils’ learning practices as evident in the two schools studied was reminiscent of notions of development and underdevelopment as characteristics of the developed and less developed nations in history.

Discussion

The findings of the study reported that training of teachers on the use of technology-based teaching techniques in classrooms increases efficiency and there is great impact that is experienced when full implementation takes place. Thus, rural schools should adopt technology in classrooms so that they can experience the new dynamics experienced by adopting modern techniques for teaching and learning. In agreement, Uzorka, Namara and Olaniyan (2023) research in Uganda argues that most instructors had low self-efficacy in the use of modern teaching techniques in classrooms. To echo findings, Barnová et al., (2020) argues that there should be a major focus on digital technologies for teachers in the professional development emphasizing on the benefits and how to manage emerging challenges that affect classroom practices. Moreover, Hennessy et al., (2022) reiterate that technology use in classrooms continue to evolve and there is need to manage current challenges that emerge in classrooms. The study emphasizes the benefits of technology for teachers and argues that there is need for more and increased attention on availability and accessibility of technology that can be used to enhance teaching and learning in classrooms. Cattaneo, Antonietti and Rauseo (2025) argue that teachers' self-efficacy on the adoption of technology in classrooms, resources for training, opportunities for training and transformative leadership roles are key drivers in the implementation of professional development programs for instructors and teachers.

The findings of the study also revealed that ICTs are not fully developed in rural schools and there is still little impact on transforming classrooms and other teaching practices. Thus, teachers in rural schools should continue adopting modern based teaching techniques and technology in classrooms to make the environment captivating and increase student outcomes. In agreement, Roll and Ifenthaler (2021) suggests that there is need for implementation of a model with multiple dimensions to enhance digital competence of teachers and instructors. Thus, the study further reiterates on technology comprehensive adoption among instructors which includes collaborative networks, positive attitude towards technology use, digital problem competence, digital problem solving and finally a self-reflection on digital communication and environment. Similarly, Çam and Koç (2024) argue that after training teachers transferred the knowledge gained to the classrooms, there was increased attention on students from the new teaching methods which included technology adoption, and that there was increased interest demonstrated by students during lessons. Thus, teachers have experienced changed classrooms from the new technology-based teaching methods which brought new insights to students when difficult and challenging topics were being taught in classrooms. To reiterate the findings, Stutchbury, et al., (2023), argued that teachers reported increased positive impact on their classroom practices, professional identity, and enhanced transformational practices that from new teaching methods in classrooms. The study findings also reported that professional development of teachers aims to provide pedagogical change among teachers so that they can make

great impact in the teaching and learning in classrooms. Finally, Fernández-Batanero, et al., (2020) reported that technology training is the key training component to enhance quality education. Thus, for effective professional development of teachers to be realized, then digital competence of teachers should be taken into consideration, because this will affect its efficacy.

Conclusions

The study concludes that teachers' professional development is very crucial and important because its adoption in schools will ease administrative work, make learning efficient, improve the quality of students' academic work, enhance performance of students in learning and assessments, and finally it would lead to improved wholistic development of schools. The study also concludes that there is urgent need for teachers to be trained in technology use in classrooms, and this includes teacher professional development which equips teachers with adequate skills, attitudes, values and knowledge on technology-based learning and teaching. The findings in this study have important implications for ICT educational practice in that it clearly revealed that the influence of TPD on school effectiveness is enormous given the positive correlation between these two aspects in that the former fosters the latter. They are thus mutually constitutive in that the educators' ICT competence levels are improved by TPD while their level of commitment to the realization of their organization's mission and goals was also buttressed. Drawing from the literature examined in this research, it followed that it is imperative for the 21st century school stakeholders to ensure that ICT educator professional development is taken seriously to align them with modern global teaching and learning trends as the world undergoes transformation. Educators thus need a high level of preparedness to deal with e-learning and related aspects if they are to remain relevant to modern day teaching and learning. Teacher professional development programs should thus focus on a wider spectrum including pedagogy and pedagogical content knowledge aspects. Given that modern day teachers are having to teach in increasingly multicultural classrooms, which place greater emphasis on integrating learner diversity in their classrooms, making more effective use of ICT for teaching, engaging more in planning within evaluative and accountability frameworks and doing more to involve parents in schools (SGBs), no matter how good the pre-service training for teachers is.

From the study findings and conclusion, the study recommends that School Management Teams in South Africa should familiarize themselves with the technology adoption policies and the training programs available, in technology-based learning, which can enhance teachers pedagogical content knowledge for use in the classroom. This information can be gathered with the rest of the staff possibly in the form of a workshop. Secondly, the study recommends that School Governing Bodies in South Africa should play a more vital role in teacher development programs by providing necessary funding, resources and infrastructures for all rural schools and school educators. This would ensure that the workshops and training programs might occur and are of a better standard as professionally trained facilitators may be contracted.

Limitations of the study

One limitation of study is that it involved ten participants who were members of the SMT, from only two rural primary schools in Gauteng. Thus, the data gathered was limited to only a few SMT's perceptions on the professional development of teachers in the use of technology in classrooms. It did not include rural primary or secondary school managers from schools from other provinces. However, the study achieved its main aim because it did not intend to carry out comparative research across other provinces.

References

Barnová, S., Krásna, S., & Čepelová, S. (2020). Digital Technologies as a Means of Teachers' Professional Development. *Online Journal for Research and Education, Special Issue 18, June 2020*, 11-17. <https://journal.phnoe.ac.at/index.php/resource/article/view/838>

Bergmark, U. (2020). Teachers' professional learning when building a research-based education: context-specific, collaborative and teacher-driven professional development. *Professional Development in Education*, 49(2), 210–224. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2020.1827011>

Bowman, M.A., Vongkulluksn, V.W., Jiang, Z., & Xie, K. (2022). Teachers' exposure to professional development and the quality of their instructional technology use: The mediating role of teachers' value and ability beliefs. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 54(2), 188–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2020.1830895>.

Bowman, M. A., Vongkulluksn, V. W., Jiang, Z., & Xie, K. (2020). Teachers' exposure to professional development and the quality of their instructional technology use: The mediating role of teachers' value and ability

- beliefs. *Journal of Research on Technology in Education*, 54(2), 188–204. <https://doi.org/10.1080/15391523.2020.1830895>
- Boyle, C., Lamprianous, L., & Boule, C. (2005). *Scaling the digital divide: Home computer technology and student achievement*. National Bureau of Economic Research working paper, No.16078.
- Çam, Ş. S., & Koç, G. (2024). Professional Development Program to Develop Teacher Educators' Technological Pedagogical Content Knowledge. *SAGE Open*, 14(2), 1-10. <https://doi.org/10.1177/21582440241242841>
- Canese, V. ., Paez , R., Amarilla , J., & Rodriguez , P. (2022). The Use of ICT in Educational Institutions in Paraguay and the Factors That Intervene. *International Journal of Emerging Technologies in Learning (IJET)*, 17(15), pp. 188–203. <https://doi.org/10.3991/ijet.v17i15.33255>
- Cattaneo, A.A.P., Antonietti, C., & Rauseo, M. (2025). How do vocational teachers use technology? The role of perceived digital competence and perceived usefulness in technology use across different teaching profiles. *Vocations and Learning* 18(5), 3-26. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12186-025-09359-4>
- Chisango, G., Marongwe, N., Mtsi, N., & Matyedi, T. E. (2019). Teachers' Perceptions of Adopting Information and Communication Technologies in Teaching and Learning at Rural Secondary Schools in Eastern Cape, South Africa. *Africa Education Review*, 17(2), 1–19. <https://doi.org/10.1080/18146627.2018.1491317>
- Cohen, L., Manion, G., & Morrison, P. (2011). *Research in Education*. San Francisco: Jossey-Bass
- Draker, P. (2010). Coming to grips with technology in society. *Journal of Information and Communication Technology*, 11(2), 119-123.
- Fernández-Batanero, J. M., Montenegro-Rueda, M., Fernández-Cerero, J., & García-Martínez, I. (2020). Digital competences for teacher professional development. Systematic review. *European Journal of Teacher Education*, 45(4), 513–531. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02619768.2020.1827389>
- Garage, R. (2006). Education and Technology: Key Issues and Debates. *Media Education Research Journal*, 3(1),104-112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-022-09971-9>
- Garage, R. (2006). Education and Technology: Key Issues and Debates. *Media Education Research Journal*, 3 (1),104-112. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11159-022-09971-9>
- Gartia, R. (2012). Continuous Professional Development: A Panacea For Teachers. *Gold for Research Thoughts*, 1(7), 1-4
- Hennessy, S., D'Angelo, S., McIntyre, N., Koomar, S., Kreimeia, A., Cao, L., & Zubairi, A. (2022). Technology use for teacher professional development in low-and middle-income countries: A systematic review. *Computers & Education Open*, 3, Article 100080. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.caeo.2022.100080>
- Hubers, M. D., D.Endedijk, M., & Van Veen, K. (2020). Effective characteristics of professional development programs for science and technology education. *Professional Development in Education*, 48(5), 827–846. <https://doi.org/10.1080/19415257.2020.1752289>
- Hussein, A. (2014). Engaging Academics in Training in Information Communication Technology (ICT): An African Experience with special focus on Uganda. *Journal of Contemporary Issues in Education*, 9(2), 39-56. <https://doi.org/10.20355/C5V01F>
- Liu, S. H., Tsai, H. C., & Huang, Y. T. (2015). Collaborative professional development of mentor teachers and pre-service teachers in relation to technology integration. *Educational Technology & Society*, 18(3), 161–172. Retrieved August 9, 2025 from <https://www.learntechlib.org/p/158856/>
- Lloyd, N. (2005). Understanding teacher professional development. *Journal of education Studies*, 6(4), 115-119. <https://doi.org/10.1002/rev3.3417>
- Lubis, B., & Yus, A. (2024). Mapping knowledge and research trend on technology adoption in higher education: A bibliometric analysis. *Education and Information Technologies*, 29(18),24415-24458. <https://dl.acm.org/doi/10.1007/s10639-024-12801-0>
- Luo, H., Zuo, M. & Wang, J. (2022) Promise and reality: using ICTs to bridge China's rural–urban divide in education. *Education Tech Research Dev* 70, 1125–1147 <https://doi.org/10.1007/s11423-022-10118-8>
- Maatuk, A.M., Elberkawi, E.K., Aljawarneh, S., Rashaideh, H., & Alharbi, H. (2024). The COVID-19 pandemic and E-learning: Challenges and opportunities from the perspective of students and instructors. *Journal of Computing in Higher Education*, 34(1), 21–38. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s12528-021-09274-2>
- Magee, R. M., Agosto, D. E., & Forte, A. (2017). *Four factors that regulate teen technology use in everyday life*. In Proceedings of the ACM Conference on Computer Supported Cooperative Work, CSCW (pp.511–522). Association for Computing Machinery. <https://doi.org/10.1145/2998181.2998310>
- Mathebula, N. Z., Moila, O., Maile, S., & Mnisi, S. (2025). Inadequate teacher training as a barrier to ICT integration in early childhood education: A case of selected primary schools in Tshwane West District Circuit 4. *International Journal of Learning, Teaching and Educational Research*, 24(3), 55–74. <https://doi.org/10.26803/ijlter.24.3.3>

- Merriam, S. (2010). *Qualitative research and case study applications in education*. San Francisco.
- Mestry, R. (2009). Technology-Assisted learning in Educational Centres. *Educational Technology Review*, 12(1), 1927-1936.
- Mestry, R., & Ndhlovu, R. (2014). The implications of the National Norms and Standards for school funding policy on equity in South African public schools. *South African Journal of Education*, 34(3), 1-11. Retrieved July 07, 2025, from http://www.scielo.org.za/scielo.php?script=sci_arttext&pid=S0256-01002014000300002.
- Morele, M. (2011). *Teacher development for school improvement: A case study of two primary schools in Johannesburg Central District* [MED dissertation, University of Johannesburg]
- Muyambi, G.C., Ramorola, M.Z. (2025) Unveiling educators' readiness to teach through Digital Media (DM): The case of South Africa. *Educ Inf Technol* **30**, 13807–13834 . <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-024-13310-w>
- Naidoo, B., & Perumal, J. (2014). Female principals leading at disadvantaged schools in Johannesburg, South Africa. *Educational Management Administration & Leadership*, 42(6), 808-824. <https://doi.org/10.1177/1741143214543202>.
- Nieuwenhuis, J. (2012). Analyzing qualitative data. In K. Maree (Ed.), *First Steps in Research* (pp. 72-80). Pretoria: Van Schaik.
- Rana, K. (2023). Rural primary teachers' perceived affordances of ICT training in Nepal. *Interactive Learning Environments*, 32(9), 5479–5493. <https://doi.org/10.1080/10494820.2023.2216739>
- Rocha-Castillo, S., Pasquel-López, C., & Heredia-Escorza, Y. (2025). Technology integration in indigenous schools without Internet access. *Contemporary Educational Technology*, 17(2), ep566. <https://doi.org/10.30935/cedtech/15945>
- Roll, M. J. J., & Ifenthaler, D. (2021). Multidisciplinary digital competencies of pre-service vocational teachers. *Empirical Research in Vocational Education and Training*, 13(1), 7-15. <https://doi.org/10.1186/s40461-021-00112-4>
- Stutchbury, K., Ebubedike, M., Amos, S., & Chamberlain, L. (2023). Professional development in the digital age: supporting improvements in teacher education through MOOCs. *Open Learning: The Journal of Open, Distance and e-Learning*, 40(1), 67–90. <https://doi.org/10.1080/02680513.2023.2195875>
- Tire, T., & Mlitwa, N. (2008). *ICT access and use in rural schools in South Africa: The Northern Cape Province*. Retrieved from <https://www.mancosa.co.za/blog/equal-education-a-conundrum-in-south-african-education/>. Accessed 7th July 2025
- Uzorka, A., & Olaniyan, A. O. (2022). Leadership role and professional development of technology. *Education and Information Technologies*, 1–11. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-022-11201-6>
- Uzorka, A., Namara, S., & Olaniyan, A. O. (2023). Modern technology adoption and professional development of lecturers. *Education and information technologies*, 1–27. Advance online publication. <https://doi.org/10.1007/s10639-023-11790-w>
- Vemic, J. (2007). Employee training and development and the learning organisation UDC331.363. *ifatUniversitatis, Economics and Organisation*, 4, 209-216.
- Wei, R. C., Darling-Hammond, L., Andree, A., Richardson, N., & Orphanos, S. (2009). *Professional learning in the learning profession: A status report on teacher development in the United States and abroad*. Dallas, TX: National Staff Development Council.
- Yin, R. (2009). *Case study research: Design and methods*. Newbury Park: Sage.